

Real-Time High-Fidelity Algorithms for Bayesian Inverse Problems Involving Shift-Invariant Systems

Sreeram Venkat, Stefan Henneking, Milinda Fernando, and Omar Ghattas
Center for Optimization, Inversion, Machine Learning, and Uncertainty for Complex Systems
Oden Institute for Computational Engineering and Sciences, The University of Texas at Austin

The University of Texas at Austin
Oden Institute for Computational Engineering and Sciences

Tsunami Model

Motivation: Design an early-warning system for tsunamis based on real-time pressure data from seafloor sensors. Target location: Cascadia subduction zone (US Pacific Northwest).

Forward Model: Acoustic-gravity wave equations derived from the linearization of the conservation of mass and momentum around hydrostatic pressure in the compressible ocean.¹

Model assumptions:

- Surface gravity wave height \ll ocean depth.
- Surface gravity wavelength \gg ocean depth.

Mixed problem:

- Solving for pressure p and velocity \mathbf{u} unknowns:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla p = \mathbf{0}$$

$$\frac{1}{K} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$$

Boundary conditions:

- ODE-type BC for wave height η at the ocean surface: $p = \rho g \eta$, $\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = u_y$
- Seafloor motion determines the vertical velocity at the sea bottom: $u_y = \frac{\partial b}{\partial t}$
- Absorbing BCs (e.g. PML) at the lateral boundary.

Fig 1: Diagram of PDE domain.

Animation of acoustic-gravity model for 2D domain with a simple Gaussian deformation.

¹ G. Lotto and E. Dunham. "High-Order Finite Difference Modeling of Tsunami Generation in a Compressible Ocean From Offshore Earthquakes". *Comput. Geosci.* 19.2 (2015), pp. 327–340.

Bayesian Inverse Problem

Given pressure recordings from sensors on the seafloor, infer the seafloor motion in the rupture zone.

- State** (velocity, pressure, wave height): $(\mathbf{u}, p, \eta) \in U$
- Parameter field** (seafloor motion): $m \in X$; $m := \partial b(\mathbf{x}, t)/\partial t$, $(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \Gamma_b \times (0, T)$
- Data** (pressure observations): $d \in Y$; $d = d(\mathbf{x}, t)$, $(\mathbf{x}, t) \in D^{\text{obs}} \subset \Gamma_b \times (0, T)$
- Observation operator:** $\mathcal{B}: U \mapsto Y$
(maps state (\mathbf{u}, p, η) to observables d) $\mathcal{B}(\mathbf{u}, p, \eta) := p(\mathbf{x}_j, t_i)$, $(\mathbf{x}_j, t_i) \in D^{\text{obs}}$; $\mathbf{x}_j \in \Gamma_b$ (sensor locations)
- Parameter-to-observable (p2o) map:** $\mathcal{F}: X \mapsto Y$
(maps parameters m to observables d) $\mathcal{F}(m) = \mathcal{B}(\mathbf{u}, p, \eta)$ s.t. (\mathbf{u}, p, η) satisfies the state system.²

Inverse model (definitions)

- Bayes' rule:** $d\mu_{\text{post}}/d\mu_{\text{prior}} \propto \pi_{\text{like}}(d|m)$
- Gaussian prior:** $d\mu_{\text{prior}} \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|m - m_{\text{prior}}\|_{\Gamma_{\text{prior}}^{-1}}^2\right)$; prior cov. $\Gamma_{\text{prior}} := \left(\delta I - \gamma \nabla^2 - \alpha \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}\right)^{-2}$
- Likelihood:** $\pi_{\text{like}}(d|m) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|\mathcal{F}m - d\|_{\Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1}}^2\right)$; additive noise $v \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Gamma_{\text{noise}})$
- Posterior measure:** $\mu_{\text{post}} = \mathcal{N}(m_{\text{MAP}}, \Gamma_{\text{post}})$; posterior covariance $\Gamma_{\text{post}} := \left(\mathcal{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} \mathcal{F} + \Gamma_{\text{prior}}^{-1}\right)^{-1}$;
and MAP point $m_{\text{MAP}} := \arg \min(-\log d\mu_{\text{post}}(m|d)) \Leftrightarrow \Gamma_{\text{post}}^{-1} m_{\text{MAP}} = \mathcal{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} d + \Gamma_{\text{prior}} m_{\text{prior}}$

Bayesian inference

Fig 2: Inferred parameter field and pressure reconstruction from synthetic noisy data in a 2D model.

² O. Ghattas and K. Willcox. "Learning physics-based models from data: Perspectives from inverse problems and model reduction". In: *Acta Numer.* 30 (2021), pp. 445–554.

Solving the Full-Scale 3D Bayesian Inverse Problem in Three Stages

Offline

Constructing the p2o map from adjoint solutions

- Time-invariant (autonomous) system:**

$$\mathcal{F}(m(\mathbf{x}, t), t_0 + \tau) = \mathcal{F}(m(\mathbf{x}, t)) = d(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

leads to a discrete \mathcal{F} matrix that is **block Toeplitz**:

$$\mathcal{F} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ F_{21} & F_{11} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ F_{31} & F_{21} & F_{11} & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ F_{N_t,1} & F_{N_t-1,1} & F_{N_t-2,1} & \dots & F_{11} \end{bmatrix}$$

- Each block F_{ij} has size $N_d \times N_m$; block lower-triangular structure is due to causality; and
 - N_d : number of sensors
 - N_m : spatial parameter dimension
 - N_t : number of time steps
- Cascadia: $N_d \sim \mathcal{O}(10^2)$, $N_m \sim \mathcal{O}(10^6)$, $N_t \sim \mathcal{O}(10^3)$
- Computing \mathcal{F} only requires N_d adjoint PDE solves, and storage is $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_d N_t)$ — savings of $\mathcal{O}(N_t)$.

Implementation in MFEM (FEM + explicit time-stepping)

Fig 3: Strong and weak scaling results on TACC's Frontera supercomputer with up to 7168 CLX nodes (401,408 cores).

- Cascadia: problem size and runtime (2048 nodes)
 - Domain size: ~ 1000 km x 100 km x 4 km
 - Mesh spacing: ~ 0.25 km x 0.25 km x 0.125 km
 - 3rd-order FE discretization: ~ 7 B state dof
 - ~ 0.06 s per time step (explicit, RK4)
 - ~ 1 min per 1000 time steps (forward or adjoint)

Offline

Pre-computing a compact representation of the posterior

How to compactly represent the posterior?

Eigenvalues of p2o map:

- Eigenvalues decaying to zero leads to instability in the inference of more oscillatory modes.
- Slow eigenvalue decay indicates informative data; does not admit efficient low-rank approximation.
- $N_m \gg N_d$, thus many parameters may fit the sparse data (ill-posedness due to lack of uniqueness).

$\dim(m) = 131,584,500$ $\dim(d) = 24,500$

Fig 4: Eigenvalues of the data misfit Hessian $\mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{F}$.

Precompute part of the posterior via **Woodbury formula**:

- $\Gamma_{\text{post}} = \Gamma_{\text{prior}} (I - \mathcal{F}^* (\Gamma_{\text{noise}} + \mathcal{F} \Gamma_{\text{prior}} \mathcal{F}^*)^{-1} \mathcal{F} \Gamma_{\text{prior}})^{-1}$
- Requires at most $N_d N_t$ MatVecs with the operator $\mathcal{K} := (\Gamma_{\text{noise}} + \mathcal{F} \Gamma_{\text{prior}} \mathcal{F}^*)$

- Need fast way of applying p2o map \mathcal{F} and its adjoint \mathcal{F}^*

Block Toeplitz structure enables fast FFT-based MatVec:

- Embed block Toeplitz matrix \mathcal{F} into a block Circulant matrix \mathcal{C}
- DFT block-diagonalizes \mathcal{C} : $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_d N_t \log N_t)$ (one-time setup cost)
- FFT of vector: $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_t \log N_t)$
- MatVec in Fourier space: $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_d N_t)$
- IFFT of vector: $\mathcal{O}(N_d N_t \log N_t)$

- No extra setup cost for \mathcal{F}^* MatVec
- Fast and scalable multi-GPU computation (Fig 5)³
- $\sim 200,000$ x speedup vs matrix-free MatVec via forward/adjoint PDE solves on Frontera CLX for ~ 100 m parameters and 25K data points

³ S. Venkat, M. Fernando, S. Henneking, and O. Ghattas. Fast and Scalable FFT-Based Multi-GPU Algorithms for Hessian Matrix-Vector Products Arising in Linear Inverse Problems Governed by Autonomous Dynamical Systems", *arXiv preprint* (2024).

Online

Real-time inference of the maximum-a-posteriori (MAP) point

Given data d , computing the MAP point in $\mathcal{O}(1)$ seconds:

$$m_{\text{MAP}} = \Gamma_{\text{post}} \mathcal{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} d = \Gamma_{\text{prior}} (I - \mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{K}^{-1} \mathcal{F} \Gamma_{\text{prior}})^{-1} \mathcal{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} d$$

Operations:

- 2x \mathcal{F}^* MatVecs: $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_d N_t)$
- 1x \mathcal{F} MatVec: $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_d N_t)$
- 1x Solve with pre-computed \mathcal{K} : $\mathcal{O}(N_d^2 N_t^2)$
- 2x Prior solves: $\mathcal{O}(N_m N_t)$

Fig 5: FFT $\mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{F}$ MatVec scaling – single GPU scaling vs. N_d, N_m, N_t and weak scaling on NVIDIA A100 40 GB GPUs.

Quantifying uncertainty:

- The pointwise variance of the posterior (diag. of Γ_{post}) can be pre-computed with a stochastic estimator.³

Surface gravity wave reconstruction:

- If needed, the gravity wave η (or another predictive quantity) can be reconstructed via push-forward of the inferred parameter field through a prediction map:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{pred}}: m \mapsto \eta$$

$$\text{with } \mu_{\text{post}(\eta)} = \mathcal{N}(\eta_{\text{MAP}}, \Gamma_{\text{post}(\eta)}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{F}_{\text{pred}} m_{\text{MAP}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{pred}} \Gamma_{\text{post}(m)} \mathcal{F}_{\text{pred}}^*)$$

- $\mathcal{F}_{\text{pred}}$ has a similar block Toeplitz structure as \mathcal{F} , admitting compact representation and fast FFT MatVecs.

⁴ E. Hallman, I. C. Ipsen, and A. K. Saibaba. "Monte Carlo Methods for Estimating the Diagonal of a Real Symmetric Matrix", *SIAM Journal on Matrix Analysis and Applications* 44 (1) (2023) 240–269.